

BM5102 | Organizational Behavior

SEMESTER 1 2020/2021

Name	: Nicholas Iswa Anak Jais
Student ID	: 20M1275
Email	: 20m1275@ubd.edu.bn
Programme	: BM5102 Organizational Behavior

Title	: Reflective Critique Report
--------------	------------------------------

Number of pages	: 8
Word count	: 2661

Reflective Critique Report

As the title entails, this paper would provide a general analysis of my personal experiences in taking Organizational Behavior as one of my core modules. As mentioned, a Reflective Report is a piece of writing that summarizes a student's critical reflection on a subject matter (Ivory Research, accessed in 2020). After three months into learning this module, I have encountered several chapters of Organizational Behavior, to call a few, there was the introductory lecture followed by the understanding of creativity and the nature of work motivations. There's no doubt this module is extremely interesting but nonetheless, the chapter that had caught my attention the most was the study on individual differences comprising personality and ability. So much so, I have incorporated them into my overall primary research on diversity within the organization for my recent Individual Analysis Report. That said within the subsequent paragraphs I would primarily discuss my experience and my overall thought in learning this chapter. Followed by the analysis of diversity in organization debate. Finally my general thoughts on taking Masters of Management thus far.

As agreed by most literature researches, learning individual differences is crucial for both the organizations and also the individuals. This is because people act differently from each other and it differs for a good range of reasons. Irrespective of where in the organization, different people have different personalities. Thus understanding this may be beneficial for the organization. For example, we are able to solve the challenges of diversity in organizations. Having said that, the study of individual differences falls under two main types which are the 'personality' and 'ability' differences. Moreover, there's also the study on nature, determinants, and consequences of individual differences for managing organizational behavior within the real world. Before coming into the chapter, my understanding of personalities and individual abilities was minimal because I have always perceived them to be fated by their innate nature. However, now I have learned that individuals are shaped by nature, are surrounded by and personalities are set by nurture. This was entirely true because I have noticed that my personalities are the same as both my parents and siblings. The studies I have encountered suggest that by understanding which part of people's personality was inherited and which part was thanks to situational factors, we are able to determine which of their personalities can or cannot be changed. Also, individual personalities are set over time not on a short term basis but a protracted term base. Therefore, it's important to find out that individual personalities are different and that we as people should accept them for what it's and try to develop effective ways to enhance them.

One of my arguments within the Individual Analysis Report of diversity within the organizations argued that feelings, thoughts, attitudes, and behaviors in an organization are laid low with the interaction of the personality of an individual similarly because the situation the individual is in. Therefore, to grasp one's personality, it's important to visualize individuals with similar personalities tend to be drawn to an organization and are more receptive to a diverse workforce, and people with conflicting personalities tend to be neglected and are more susceptible to resistance to change. This philosophy was initially introduced by George & Jones (2012) and that they presented this under the attraction-selection-attrition framework. Henceforth, it's without a doubt that I believe individual differences argument plays a vital role

in an organization, especially in understanding diversity. Thus, within the next paragraph, we'd check out the diversity within the organization debate.

According to the Association of College and Research Libraries (2012) suggest that diversity is a vital component of any civil society where it's more than an ethical imperative; it's a global necessity. Everyone can benefit from diversity, and diverse populations have to be supported in order that they can reach their full potential for themselves and their communities. Therefore, coming to the current specific chapter plays a vital part in my daily life especially coming from a culturally diverse background. That said, there are key components to understanding diversity. In a nutshell, the requirement for diversity within the organizations comes as a result of free movement of labor, globalization, and also the fight for human rights by certain minority groups who feel excluded from the employment sector. (Foma, 2014; Sri Handayani, 2017; Yadav & Lenka, 2020). Moreover, Henry & Evans (2007) argued that workplace diversity emerged mainly to further the availability of equal opportunities within the workplace, and this human right philosophy aimed towards ensuring that organizations make the foremost out of the difference from a diverse workforce, rather than losing talent which could assist the organizations to be more efficient and effective. additionally, increased mobility and interaction of people from diverse backgrounds, as a results of improved economic and political systems, and also the recognition of human rights by all national entities has placed serious pressure for organizations to embrace diversity within the workplace. This is because diversity introduces heterogeneity that has to be nurtured, cultivated, and appreciated thanks to the means of accelerating organizational effectiveness within the competitive world.

Moreover, I feel there are several other beneficial factors that affect the organizational performance of a corporation if they introduce more diverse policies. However, coming to this topic, I have understood that diversity falls under two levels, which is the more demographic characteristics like gender, age, and race which is stated as surface-level diversity, but as globalizations constantly prepare us for changes, deep-level diversity has gained more attention nowadays, this includes individual differences, comprising of personalities, values, sexual preference, and individual abilities. Therefore, it's important to notice this distinction. After understanding the two distinctions, we are able to move forward to the advantages.

I've noted that when doing my research on diversity, there have been inconsistencies between what varieties of benefits of diversity, also, most literature reviews primarily shift their focus on the advantages of managing workforce diversity. Although this receives no negative connotation, I find it really intriguing on why there was little research on the implications on the individual level. However, I've realized that this was because it involves a completely new perspective instead of specializing in managing workplace diversity. Therefore, I too included just the advantages of managing workplace diversity. That said, I feel considerable research into the individual perspective shouldn't be neglected. Henceforth, there have been several interpretations of the advantages of managing workplace diversity. for instance, I have included Mullins (2010) and Daft (2010) as cited from Sri Handayani (2017) system review of workplace diversity management proposed several positive effects of employee diversity in an organization, namely: (1) workplace diversity actually promotes work and value relationship effectively by employing a stronger pool of talents; (2) workplace diversity enhances customer relationship; (3)

workplace diversity improves creativity, flexibility, and innovation; (4) workplace diversity reduces the costs associated with turnover, absenteeism, and lawsuit; and (5) workplace diversity promotes the development and sustainable business advantage. That being said, the overall consensus suggests that diversity contains a positive implication for an organization.

After completing my Individual Analysis Report, I was able to reflect on several key challenges that I have faced during the initial period. Because we were currently in a global pandemic, our lecturer decided that all research studies are to be conducted solely on secondary sources. This eventually became my primary focus because previously I had done an initial outline stating that I would have done primary source-based research because I would be getting reliable and valid data due to first-hand experiences. But again, going back to global pandemic circumstances, I was able to efficiently gain secondary sources via books, journals, and online base sources. Obviously, I was worried that my research would primarily concentrate on diversity in an organization from a broad perspective, not locally. I wasn't able to apply the data I have gathered within the local space. However, to my surprise, since most literature reviews were consistent in what the implications of workplace diversity were, which was mainly positive, I believe that it would be applicable here. That being said, I was satisfied with my Individual Analysis Report. Moving on, in the following paragraph, I would touch on my experience in my Group Case Study Project.

Highlighting the main challenges that every student faces was the midst of the global pandemic. It disrupts the overall structure of the module. Now we were told that this module would be hundred percent coursework. Thus, this too affected the group-project where each group was tasked with a specific research topic they have to abide by. Initially, my group study focuses on the effect of electronic technology on the prevalence of sexual harassment. Bear in mind that within my group it was all male dominated and comprised three individuals including myself. Therefore, at the early stage, heads were turned due to the complexity and severity of the topic issue. But months have passed and we received a "bad news" where we were told to revise our initial topic since the lecturer was worried that due to the implications and sensitivity of the topic, thus, initial research has gone in vain. However, that did not deter our motivation since now, we were able to choose any particular topic that we were more comfortable with. Which was the study on workplace cyberbullying. The drafting period was a breeze since all works were to be conducted on secondary sources. This was because there was a considerable amount of literature research on workplace cyberbullying. Initially, amongst a group of three individual, we agreed that the task was to be divided amongst us to enable more efficient and productive work. As supported by Max Weber theory of bureaucracy where segregation duties allows for discipline and specialization of duties.

Additionally, we agreed that communication would be at the maximum but due to time constraints and coupled with other module assignments, we've neglected who does more on what. Plus under limited supervision, seems to be a problem. Because we believe that, everyone should trust their members, as supported by McGregor Theory X. But as soon as there was more flexibility and the absence of a leadership role, none took the initiative to start with the first draft. Eventually, it got pushed to the second last week of submission, where I had to communicate amongst the other two colleagues that we should start with our Group Project. As time passed by,

work became slow and inconsistent, thus I took leadership and began the work myself. I have realized that my colleagues were jumping on the bandwagon of the free-riding movement. This was supported with the prisoners dilemma argument, where individuals would always try to defect in order to save themselves. Again, this did not deter my motivation but more worried about the contribution of others, since this is a group project, everyone needs to contribute. Finally, on the last date of the submission, we were able to complete the task in a nick of time despite it being late due to miscommunication amongst each other on who decides to submit the work.

Looking back at that experience, I have brushed my strengths and notified my weaknesses too. I was able to strengthen my communication skills and become a more proactive individual than I was before. This was evident with the initiative to take the leadership role amongst my peers. However, it also pointed out my weaknesses too, which was the need to help everyone and neglect my individual work. Although it received no negative connotation, it has become a double-edge-sword, leading to me doing most of the work rather than giving it to my colleagues. Moreover, although the group work was deemed a success, there were serious personal implications that I have learned. I've learned that each individual is different everywhere, especially in task division. This was supported by the individual differences chapter I have learned during the introductory lecture followed by reading up the organizational behavior journals and books. I.e. Robbins & Judge (2013). Finally my final thoughts on this experience was that I would have not changed my ways in doing research but finding the right individuals to work on a research should be taken strongly next time. Plus, I should in fact improve more on my personality and values in the division of tasks. There, I have come to a realization that although there were hiccups, I would take the positive outcomes with me into the next assignment.

Finally, after reviewing my reflective analysis on the chapters thought, then followed by analysis of my Individual Analysis Report, and finally my Group Case Study Report, this part of the paper I would talk about my motivations on pursuing Masters of Management thus far. Looking back at my experience for the past three months, my motivations for pursuing my postgraduate have not changed but improved. Earlier on the module, we were tasked to provide a one-paper description as to why we pursue our postgraduate studies. Initially, I have stated that my motivation in taking Masters, especially in Management, was based on McClelland's Need Theory. According to McClelland (1961) as cited from Ramlall (2004) review on employees motivation suggests three needs that affect individual motivation, which are achievement, power, and affiliation. As the theory mentioned, the need for 'achievement' was defined as the drive to excel, to achieve in relation to a set of standards, to strive to succeed. Next, he suggested that the need for 'power' was defined as the need to make others behave in a way that they would not have behaved otherwise. Finally, the theory argued that the need for 'affiliation' is the desire for friendly and close interpersonal relationships. Therefore, it is up for one's interpretation as to how one weighs in these three needs.

Previously mentioned in that paper, I had used McLelland's Need Theory and weight in my needs using the SWOT analysis where I have mentioned that my strength was "Personal Achievement" and it ultimately ties in with my career aspiration to progress higher and opportunities attached to postgraduate studies. After three months, nothing has changed and I

still believe that my motivation in taking up this challenge was solely for personal achievement. Next I have mentioned my weakness which was the power argument, this was because a power-hungry attitude was deemed impartial to my overall motivation. But as time passes by, a strong leadership abilities is seen as a necessity. Thus my overall attitude towards power has considerably changed. This was supported by McClelland (1961) in which he argued that in order to be an effective business manager, “power-hungry” attitude is crucial. Then I have included the opportunity aspect where I tied it with the need for “affiliation” in which I have mentioned that social relationship and activities is seen as a positive. This is true because through social networking has helped me to improve my communication skills which in turn positively affected my motivation. Therefore, I can say that my motivation for pursuing masters has not changed but it has improved slightly within these couple months.

To conclude this paper, a summary would suffice. As mentioned, I have included my personal experience in the teaching materials, individual analysis and my group project. Although there were hiccups, I believe that this is a lesson for the future, good and the bad, I have realized this is just part of the learning process. Having said that, I stated that my motivation so far has been undeterred but there is room for improvements especially on the personal level. My overall expectations for taking Organizational Behavior as one of my core modules has been an eye-opening experience. It has taught me several key components to organizational performance which I would take with me for the future. I was particularly fascinated with the individual differences argument and the diversity in organization debate. Therefore this paper concludes with the need for reflective report because it can help with career aspirations and improve personal attributes.

Bibliography

Association of College and Research Libraries. (2012). *Cultural Competency for Academic*

Libraries. ACRL Diversity Standards. Retrieved November 22, 2020, from

www.ala.org/acrl/standards/diversity

Daft, R. (n.d.). *Management* (Ninth ed.). Cengage Learning.

Foma, E. (2014). Impact of Workplace Diversity. *Review Integrative Business & Economics*, 3(1), 402-410.

Fruend, J. (1968). *The Sociology of Max Weber*. The Penguin Press.

George, J. M., & Jones, G. R. (2012). *Understanding and Managing Organizational Behavior* (Sixth ed.). Pearson Education Limited.

- Handayani, S., Suharnomo, Yuniawan, A., Wahyudi, S., & Wikaningrum, T. (2017, December). systematic literature review of managing workplace diversity for sustaining organizational competitive advantage. *International Journal of Mechanical Engineering and Technology*, 8(2), 398-406.
- Henry, O., & Evans, A. J. (2007, June 27). Critical review of literature on workforce diversity. *African Journal of Business Management*, 72-76.
- Ivory Research. (2020). *How to Write 1st Class Reflective Reports*. Ivory Research. Retrieved November 22, 2020, from <https://www.ivoryresearch.com/library/other-articles/reflective-reports-how-to-write-1st-class-reflective-reports/>
- Kopelman, R. E., Prottas, D. J., & Davis, A. L. (2012). Further Development of a Measure of Theory X and Y Managerial Assumptions. *Journal of Managerial Issues*, 24(4), 450-470.
- Leadley, S. (2015, June). Reflection on Diversity and Organizations. *Reference & User Service Quarterly*, 54(4), 6-10. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5860/rusq.54n4.6>
- Lei, N. L. (2012, October 18). *Organizational Behavior Academic Reflective essay*. My Metamorphosis. Retrieved November 22, 2020, from <https://sites.google.com/site/nglinlei/semester-2/organizational-behavior>
- McClelland, D. (1961). *The Achieving Society*. New York Free Press.
- McGregor, D. M. (1960). *The Human Side of Enterprise*. McGraw-Hill.
- Mullins, L. J. (2010). *Management & Organizational Behavior*. Pearson Education Limited.
- Musa, S. F., & Idris, D. S. (2020). Addressing Issues of Unemployment in Brunei: The Mismatch Between Employers Expectations and Employees Aspirations. *International*

Journal of Asian Business and Information Management (IJABIM), 11(2), 88-101.
doi:10.4018/IJABIM.2020040106

Ramlall, S. (204). A Review of Employee Motivation Theories and their Implications for Employee Retention within Organizations. *The Journal of American Academy of Business*.

Robbins, S. P., & Judge, T. A. (2013). *Organizational Behavior* (15th ed.). Pearson Limited.

Yadav, S., & Lenka, U. (2020, April). Workforce diversity: From a literature review to future research agenda. *Journal of Indian Business Research*.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/340991087_Workforce_diversity_from_a_literature_review_to_future_research_agenda?enrichId=rgreq-b5ebfead6294b1e3ec255d3d304134d8-XXX&enrichSource=Y292ZXJQYWdlOzM0MDk5MTA4NztBUzo5MTAwOTEyNDcxNzM2MzJAMTU5Mzk5NDA3MDgxN

Yadav, S., & Lenka, U. (2020, May). Diversity management: A systematic Review. *Equality, Diversity and Inclusion: An International Journal*.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341416156_Diversity_management_a_systematic_review?enrichId=rgreq-f8a32c8de8f27b2d80d7f69d55df9b64-XXX&enrichSource=Y292ZXJQYWdlOzM0MTQxNjE1NjtBUzo4OTM2ODE5MzAzNjY5NzZAMTU5MDA4MTc4NDI2OQ%3D%3D&el=1_x_2&_esc=publicat